

Impact of mild hydrothermal aging on kinetics of NH₃, NO, SO₂ and CO oxidation reactions on Cu/SSZ-13 catalyst

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Abstract

Cu/SSZ-13 is a catalyst commonly used for selective catalytic reduction (SCR) of nitrogen oxides (NO_x) in diesel engine exhaust. Standard configurations are based on SCR preceded by an oxidation catalyst, however, a close-coupled SCR configuration appears relevant for upcoming regulations addressing cold-start emissions. Two often discussed ion-exchanged Cu sites in Cu/SSZ-13 are denoted ZCuOH and Z₂Cu, where Z represents an Al atom in the zeolite framework. Mild hydrothermal aging (HTA) causes Cu redistribution within the catalyst; ZCuOH sites transform into more stable Z₂Cu species. In this work, the effect of mild HTA on NH₃, NO, SO₂, and CO oxidation is studied on a commercial Cu/SSZ-13 sample. Temperature-programmed reaction experiments, performed in a lab reactor, and previously published catalyst characterization data using H₂-TPR, NH₃-TPD, and DRIFTS were used to build and validate a mathematical model. It couples the kinetics of the oxidation reactions with ZCuOH and Z₂Cu concentration evolution during mild HTA. The model uses two distinct rate coefficients for ZCuOH and Z₂Cu sites, allowing prediction of the catalyst activity during aging. The results suggest that the rate coefficients for the studied reactions on Z₂Cu are effectively nil, so the observed activity in NH₃, NO, SO₂, and CO oxidation can be attributed solely to ZCuOH sites.

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1 **1. Introduction**

Selective catalytic reduction (SCR) is the current standard technology for abatement of nitrogen oxides (NO_x) from diesel engine vehicles exhaust and Cu/SSZ-13 catalysts are commercially used for this purpose [1, 2, 3]. The overall reaction for the standard SCR can be written as:

2 Current configurations of diesel exhaust aftertreatment systems include at
3 least the following units: a diesel oxidation catalyst (DOC), a diesel particulate
4 filter (DPF), an SCR catalyst, and an ammonia slip catalyst (ASC) [4]. In
5 such a configuration, the SCR catalyst may face hydrothermal aging during
6 regeneration of the diesel particulate filter [2, 5]. Recently, in an effort to reduce
7 cold-start emissions of NO_x , a close-coupled configuration (cc-SCR) has been
8 proposed, where the SCR is placed directly at the outlet of the engine, upstream
9 of the other catalyst components. This approach has been shown to effectively
10 reduce NO_x slip due to accelerated catalyst warm-up [6, 7, 8]. However, the
11 catalyst is exposed to higher temperatures and increased concentrations of CO,
12 hydrocarbons, and soot, as well as SO_2 , in the close-coupled configuration.
13 Thus, the oxidation reactions that would normally take place on an upstream
14 DOC become relevant for a close-coupled SCR catalyst and co-determine its
15 performance. Therefore quantifying the oxidation rates over an SCR catalyst is
16 ultimately needed to predict overall efficiency.

17 The Cu/SSZ-13 catalysts used for SCR have Cu ions exchanged into the
18 structure of the SSZ-13 zeolite. Copper can be present in the catalyst in the
19 form of mono- and multinuclear framework sites, as well as extra-framework
20 CuO nanoparticles [9, 10, 11]. Two main framework sites are often described
21 as present in the Cu/SSZ-13 catalyst: Z_2Cu and ZCuOH [2, 3], where Z rep-
22 resents an Al atom in the zeolite framework. Their distribution in the catalyst

23 depends on various factors, such as the silica-to-alumina ratio and Cu loading
 24 [12, 13, 14, 15]. It has been shown that the Z_2Cu species is preferably populated
 25 first at lower Cu loadings, followed by $ZCuOH$ at higher loadings [9]. Cu ions
 26 can be solvated by H_2O and NH_3 , which provides these species with mobility
 27 in zeolite cages. Literature shows that the solvated species, as well as static
 28 dimers and oxygen-bridged dicopper (Cu-O-Cu) species, are prevalent in the
 29 low-temperature region, whereas at higher temperatures when H_2O and NH_3
 30 would desorb from the catalyst, monomeric Cu bound to the zeolite has been
 31 proposed as the active SCR site [10, 11, 16, 17, 18].

32 Several mechanisms lead to a loss of Cu/SSZ-13 catalyst activity during its
 33 lifetime. The most important pathways are hydrothermal aging (HTA) and
 34 sulfur poisoning [1, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23]. Sulfur poisoning is related to SO_x in
 35 the exhaust gas. The SCR catalyst performance after sulfur poisoning can be
 36 partially restored by periodic high-temperature regeneration treatment [1, 24,
 37 25]. When oxygen is present in the feed, SO_2 can be oxidized to SO_3 . Previous
 38 studies suggest that the extent and mechanism of sulfur poisoning on Cu/SSZ-
 39 13 by SO_2 and SO_3 is not equivalent, with more severe impact when the feed
 40 contains SO_3 [1, 25]. There is also evidence that Z_2Cu sites are less susceptible
 41 to sulfur poisoning than $ZCuOH$, and that the poisoning under dry conditions
 42 is strongly correlated with SO_2 oxidation on $ZCuOH$ sites [1].

Mild hydrothermal aging leads mainly to the transformation of Cu sites [1].
 In particular, the Cu ions tend to move from $ZCuOH$ sites to more stable Z_2Cu
 positions, which is accompanied by a loss of Brønsted acid sites ZH [1, 19, 26,
 27, 28]:

43 Temperatures above 750 °C accelerate the dealumination of the zeolite, which
 44 has a more severe impact on the zeolite structure and catalyst activity [23].

45 Framework Cu site distribution affects the SCR catalyst operation in several
 46 ways. Ammonia adsorption and temperature programmed desorption (TPD) ex-
 47 periments suggest that after mild HTA, NH_3 desorption occurs at lower tempera-

48 tures, which correlates with the transformation from ZCuOH towards Z₂Cu sites
49 by which the density of strong Brønsted acid sites decreases [2, 26, 27, 28, 29],
50 see equation (2). While the SCR reaction itself seems to be independent of
51 ZCuOH or Z₂Cu site type at low temperature, the NH₃ oxidation activity de-
52 creases with ZCuOH-to-Z₂Cu transformation during catalyst aging [22, 1, 2]. At
53 high temperatures, a lower NH₃ oxidation rate was observed on aged samples
54 and this phenomenon was shown to positively affect NO_x conversion during the
55 stoichiometric SCR reaction, as less NH₃ was consumed in parasitic oxidation
56 [1, 2].

57 Recently, Khurana et al. [30] conducted a study on NO oxidation under
58 dry conditions using Cu/SSZ-13 samples with various densities of Z₂Cu and
59 ZCuOH species. Although neither of the monomeric sites was directly linked
60 to the reaction, the amount of ZCuOH species affected the oxidation activity
61 indirectly as a precursor to Cu-oxo dimers, which were identified as the active
62 sites for NO oxidation. In contrast, the Z₂Cu site was found to be inactive in
63 NO oxidation [12, 31]. This is consistent with a study of Akter et al. [32], in
64 which Cu/CHA samples with lower Cu loadings showed no detectable dry NO
65 oxidation activity (due to practically all Cu sites being populated as Z₂Cu),
66 while the samples with higher Cu loadings (containing substantial amount of
67 ZCuOH sites) were active.

68 CO oxidation has been mostly studied as a titration technique for quantifying
69 proximal ZCuOH sites and Cu dimers. Recent studies imply that at lower
70 temperatures under dry conditions, ZCuOH sites are indirectly responsible for
71 CO oxidation to CO₂ [30, 33, 34]. Iacobone et al. [33] further suggests that
72 after adding water, both Z₂Cu and ZCuOH species are hydrolyzed and therefore
73 active in CO₂ evolution. However, at higher temperatures, the water-mobilized
74 species become less stable, and static Cu species become active sites for the
75 oxidation reactions [34].

76 The goal of this work is to investigate the impact of mild hydrothermal aging
77 on the steady-state kinetics of NH₃, NO, SO₂, and CO oxidation in a range
78 of SCR operating temperatures. We compare the trends in catalytic activity

Figure 1: Cross-section view of the Cu/SSZ-13 washcoat on monolith channels, obtained by scanning electron microscopy. Red lines indicate the substrate/coating boundaries, yellow lines mark external surface of the coated catalyst layer.

79 for the individual reactions and identify similarities between them. We aim
 80 to develop a model that couples the Cu site transformation kinetics with the
 81 kinetics of oxidation reactions on individual Cu sites, allowing the prediction of
 82 the evolution of SCR catalyst activity during mild hydrothermal aging.

83 2. Experimental setup

84 The Cu/SSZ-13 catalyst used in the experiments was supplied by Cummins
 85 Inc and washcoated on a cordierite monolith structure with square channels and
 86 a cell density of 300 cells per square inch (cpsi). The Si:Al ratio in the SSZ-13
 87 zeolite was 9.5 [26] and the copper loading was 3.1 wt.% (484 $\mu\text{mol/g}$ coat-
 88 ing) [29]. Smaller cylindrical samples were obtained by core-drilling the original
 89 monolith; the sample geometry can be found in Table 1. The geometrical pa-
 90 rameters for the channel and catalytic coating were evaluated from cross-section
 91 SEM image analysis, Figure 1. Procedure used for the washcoat geometry cal-
 92 culation is described in detail in Supplementary Material. This ensures that the

93 correct amount of active Cu/SSZ-13 catalyst is considered in our calculations
94 and enables proper scaling to different catalyst loadings (e.g., other monolith
95 configurations or catalyst powder tests).

96 The samples were wrapped with ceramic fiber strings and placed into a
97 quartz tube located inside a Lindberg BlueM tube furnace with 30 cm long
98 heated zone. The catalyst temperature was measured with K-type Omega ther-
99 mocouples placed upstream and downstream of the monolith. Tubing upstream
100 and downstream of the reactor was heated to 150 °C using heat tape, and in-
101 sulated to prevent water condensation on the surface of the tubing. An FTIR
102 MKS 2030 was used to monitor the reactor outlet concentrations of CO, CO₂,
103 H₂O, NO, NO₂, NH₃, SO₂ and SO₃.

104 Before the experiments, the samples were degreened by exposing to 10 %
105 O₂, 7 % H₂O, 8 % CO₂ and balance N₂ at 550 °C for 4 h. This catalyst state
106 is referred to as "degreened". The mild hydrothermal aging exposure was per-
107 formed with the same gas concentrations but at 600 °C for 10 or 25 h. These
108 hydrothermally aged samples are referred to as "HTA-600 10 h" and "HTA-600
109 25 h", respectively. The catalytic activity of the degreened and aged samples
110 was tested using the selected component – 200 ppm NH₃, 200 ppm NO, 200 ppm
111 CO, or 50 ppm SO₂ – in a mixture of 10 % O₂, 8 % CO₂, and 7 or 0 % H₂O (wet
112 or dry, respectively). Prior to each reaction experiment, the sample was treated
113 in 10 % O₂ at 500 °C for 1 h to ensure that Cu is oxidized to Cu^{II}. Steady-state
114 conversions were then measured at 200, 250, 300, 350, 400, 450, 500, and 550 °C.
115 At each temperature, the catalyst activity was stabilized for approximately 30
116 minutes to reach steady state. As will be demonstrated later in Section 4, cata-
117 lyst aging during the reaction experiments was negligible compared to the HTA
118 procedure lasting several hours at 600 °C. The total gas flow rate in all reactor
119 experiments was 1360 cm³/min at standard conditions, corresponding to GHSV
120 of 62 000 h⁻¹.

121 The quantification of sites was adopted from Wei et al. [2] who studied
122 the SCR reaction (1) on the same degreened and hydrothermally aged catalyst
123 samples. NO+NH₃ temperature programmed reduction (NO+NH₃-TPR) was

124 used to count the total amount of Cu reducible by NH_3+NO , which corresponds
125 to the combination of ZCuOH and Z_2Cu [35, 36, 37].

126 After hydrothermal aging, the total amount of SCR reducible Cu did not
127 change, which indicates that no Cu oxide particles were formed during our HTA
128 treatments in the sample, and that the ion-exchanged ZCuOH and Z_2Cu species
129 are responsible for any changes in Cu distribution

130 After hydrothermal aging, the total amount of SCR reducible Cu did not
131 change, which indicates that no Cu oxide particles were formed during our
132 HTA treatments in the sample and that the ion-exchanged ZCuOH and Z_2Cu
133 species are responsible for the change in Cu distribution. Z_2Cu site density was
134 measured by H_2 -TPR experiments as proposed by Luo et al. [29]. The ZCuOH
135 density was obtained by subtracting the amount of Z_2Cu calculated by H_2 -TPR
136 from the total reducible Cu amount obtained by the $\text{NO}+\text{NH}_3$ -TPR experiments
137 reported by Wei et al. [2]. Brønsted acid site (ZH) densities were calculated by
138 the amount of NH_3 desorbed at high temperature during NH_3 temperature
139 programmed desorption (NH_3 -TPD) experiments previously published [2]. A
140 shift from high- to low-temperature NH_3 desorption peaks correlated with the
141 decrease of ZH site concentration that accompanies Cu transfer from ZCuOH
142 towards Z_2Cu species.

143 3. Mathematical model

144 3.1. Transport equations

145 The SCR monolith sample was described using a heterogeneous 1D plug-flow
146 model considering a coated catalyst layer on the channel wall [38, 39, 40, 41, 42].
147 The model consists of component mole balances in the flowing gas (3), inside
148 the pores of the catalytic coating (4) and on the surface of the catalyst (5), as
149 well as enthalpy balances of the solid phase (6) and of the flowing gas (7).

$$\frac{\partial c_k(z, t)}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial(u \cdot c_k)}{\partial z} + \frac{k_c a}{\varepsilon^g} c \left(y_k^s - y_k \right), \quad k = 1, \dots, N_k \quad (3)$$

Table 1: Parameters of the investigated Cu/SSZ-13 catalyst sample

Parameter	Value
length, L	2.9 cm
diameter, D	0.75 cm
channel density	320 cpsi
channel void fraction, ε^g	0.679
wall thickness	150 μm
washcoat thickness	50 μm
washcoat density, ρ_w	800 kg/m^3
washcoat vol. fraction in solid phase, φ_w	0.361
total Z site concentration in washcoat, Ω_Z	837 mol/m^3

$$\frac{\partial c_k^s(z, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{k_c a}{\varepsilon^s(1 - \varepsilon^g)\varphi_w} c(y_k - y_k^s) + \frac{1}{\varepsilon^s} \sum_{i=1}^{N_i} \nu_{k,i} r_i, \quad k = 1, \dots, N_k \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{\partial \theta_m(z, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{\Omega_Z} \sum_{i=1}^{N_i} \nu_{m,i}^\theta r_i, \quad m = 1, \dots, N_m \quad (5)$$

$$\rho^s c_p^s \frac{\partial T_s(z, t)}{\partial t} = \lambda^s \frac{\partial^2 T_s}{\partial z^2} + \frac{k_h a}{1 - \varepsilon^g} (T - T_s) - \varphi_w \sum_{i=1}^{N_i} \Delta H_{r,i} r_i \quad (6)$$

$$\rho c_p \frac{\partial T(z, t)}{\partial t} = -u \rho c_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} + \frac{k_h a}{\varepsilon^g} (T_s - T) \quad (7)$$

150 The partial differential equations are complemented with the following bound-
151 ary conditions: (i) $c_k = c_k^{\text{in}}$ and $T = T^{\text{in}}$ at the inlet ($z = 0$), and (ii) $\partial T^s / \partial z = 0$
152 at both inlet and outlet ($z = 0$ and $z = L$, respectively). All the reactions con-
153 sidered are exothermic. Though the adiabatic increase of temperature is within
154 2°C for the low reactant concentrations examined in this work, the enthalpy
155 balances were not excluded, therefore this model is general at a negligible addi-
156 tional computational cost.

157 The mass (k_c) and heat (k_h) transfer coefficients' profiles along the mono-
 158 lith channel are calculated using correlations proposed by Ramanathan et al.
 159 [43]. The numerical solution of the partial differential equations is obtained
 160 by the finite difference method with 20 spatial discretization intervals using a
 161 semi-implicit integration scheme with quasi-linearization of reaction rates, im-
 162 plemented in Fortran.

163 3.2. Reaction kinetics

164 The reaction kinetics are incorporated into the model equations through
 165 reaction rates r_i , see the right-hand sides of equations (4), (5), and (6). Thus, the
 166 reaction terms r_i affect concentrations of gas and surface components, including
 167 Cu sites speciation. The considered reactions and their rate laws r_i are listed
 168 in Table 2.

169 The kinetics of Cu site transformations during mild hydrothermal aging
 170 (HTA) of Cu/SSZ-13 catalyst is considered first order in ZCuOH as well as in
 171 Brønsted acid sites ZH, see reaction R_{HTA} in Table 2. The aging rate law is
 172 in agreement with the aging kinetics model proposed by Daya et al. [27]. The
 173 total number of Z sites (i.e., Al atoms in the zeolite framework) remains constant
 174 during mild hydrothermal aging:

$$1 = \theta_{\text{ZCuOH}} + \theta_{\text{Z}_2\text{Cu}} + \theta_{\text{ZH}} \quad (8)$$

Note that the dimensionless site concentrations θ_{ZCuOH} , $\theta_{\text{Z}_2\text{Cu}}$ and θ_{ZH} are normalized by Ω_Z , which is the total concentration of Z sites present in the zeolite (moles of sites per volume of catalytic coating). The calculation takes into account the number of Z sites present in each species. Thus, the concentration of Cu sites in the form of ZCuOH can be expressed as $\theta_{\text{ZCuOH}} \Omega_Z$ and in the form of Z₂Cu as $\frac{1}{2} \theta_{\text{Z}_2\text{Cu}} \Omega_Z$. The concentration of framework Cu sites is assumed constant:

$$\theta_{\text{ZCuOH}} + \frac{1}{2} \theta_{\text{Z}_2\text{Cu}} = \text{constant} \quad (9)$$

175 The kinetic parameters for Cu site transformation during mild hydrothermal
 176 aging were evaluated from ZCuOH and Z₂Cu site concentrations measured in the

177 degreened and aged catalyst sample by the characterization techniques described
 178 in Section 2.

Table 2: Rate laws considered for NH₃, NO, SO₂ and CO oxidation reactions on Cu/SSZ-13 catalyst. The reaction rates r_i are calculated from local component mole fractions in washcoat pores y_k^s ; the superscript "s" is omitted here for the sake of brevity

	Reaction	Rate law
R _{HTA}	$\text{ZCuOH} + \text{ZH} \longrightarrow \text{Z}_2\text{Cu} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$	$r_{\text{HTA}} = k_{\text{HTA}} \exp\left(-\frac{E_{\text{a,HTA}}}{RT}\right) \theta_{\text{ZCuOH}} \theta_{\text{ZH}} \Omega_{\text{Z}}$
R1	$2\text{NH}_3 + \frac{3}{2}\text{O}_2 \longrightarrow \text{N}_2 + 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	$r_1 = k_1 \exp\left(-\frac{E_{\text{a,1}}}{RT}\right) y_{\text{NH}_3} y_{\text{O}_2}$
R2	$\text{NO} + \frac{1}{2}\text{O}_2 \longleftrightarrow \text{NO}_2$	$r_2 = k_2 \exp\left(-\frac{E_{\text{a,2}}}{RT}\right) \left(y_{\text{NO}} y_{\text{O}_2}^{0.5} - \frac{y_{\text{NO}_2}}{K_2^{\text{eq}}}\right)$
R3	$\text{SO}_2 + \frac{1}{2}\text{O}_2 \longleftrightarrow \text{SO}_3$	$r_3 = k_3 \exp\left(-\frac{E_{\text{a,3}}}{RT}\right) \left(y_{\text{SO}_2} y_{\text{O}_2}^{0.5} - \frac{y_{\text{SO}_3}}{K_3^{\text{eq}}}\right)$
R4	$\text{CO} + \frac{1}{2}\text{O}_2 \longrightarrow \text{CO}_2$	$r_4 = k_4 \exp\left(-\frac{E_{\text{a,4}}}{RT}\right) y_{\text{CO}} y_{\text{O}_2}$

The employed steady-state reaction kinetics of NH₃, NO, SO₂, and CO oxidation are listed in Table 2. NO and SO₂ oxidation may become limited by thermodynamic equilibrium, while NH₃ and CO oxidation are practically irreversible in the studied range of temperatures. The reaction i takes place on ZCuOH and Z₂Cu sites with different rates and the overall pre-exponential factor k_i is obtained as a combination reflecting individual Cu site concentrations:

$$k_i = k_{i,\text{ZCuOH}} \theta_{\text{ZCuOH}}^n \Omega_{\text{Z}} + k_{i,\text{Z}_2\text{Cu}} \frac{1}{2} \theta_{\text{Z}_2\text{Cu}}^n \Omega_{\text{Z}} \quad (10)$$

179 As can be seen in Table 2, the activation energy was considered site-independent
 180 because the slope of conversion-vs-temperature curves measured with the de-
 181 greened and aged catalyst sample did not change significantly.

182 The proposed scaling of catalyst activity with the number of sites does not
 183 depend on a particular rate limiting step (adsorption, surface reaction, or des-
 184orption). On the other hand, the number of sites involved in the reaction (single
 185 vs. dual Cu site mechanism) might affect the dependence on the site concentra-
 186tion. It has been reported that the low-temperature SCR mechanism involves
 187mobile Cu dimers [16], which leads to 2nd order in Cu site concentration [37].
 188The role of Cu dimers was reported and confirmed at lower temperatures (below

189 250 °C), mainly in the presence of water and/or ammonia that solvate and mobi-
 190 lize Cu ions. It is known that another reaction mechanism evolves on Cu/SSZ-13
 191 at higher temperatures [44]. Our work covers a wide range of operating temper-
 192 atures up to 550 °C and a significant steady-state conversion of NO, CO, SO₂
 193 and NH₃ is achieved only above 250 °C. Thus, the impact of the low-temperature
 194 mechanism on our results is minor. Furthermore, 1st order in Cu site concen-
 195 tration is expected for oxidation reactions involving Eley-Rideal mechanism on
 196 single atom catalysts [45]. Thus, we first performed computations assuming 1st
 197 order in Cu site concentration using $n = 1$ in equation (10). Subsequently, we
 198 repeated the simulations considering 2nd order in Cu site concentration using
 199 $n = 2$ in equation (10) and compared the results of both approaches.

The kinetic parameters for individual sites were evaluated by minimizing the differences between the measured and simulated outlet concentrations of the key component k in the given reaction (NH₃, NO, CO or SO₂), considering a set of data points j at temperatures 200–550 °C. The least-squares approach was employed, defining the objective function S as:

$$S = \sum_{j=1}^{N_j} \left(y_{k,j}^{\text{sim}} - y_{k,j}^{\text{exp}} \right)^2 \quad (11)$$

200 A simplex method [46] was used for minimization of the objective function
 201 S individually for each reaction. The procedure included the following steps.
 202 (i) Using the measured data for the degreened sample, optimum activation en-
 203 ergy $E_{a,i}$ was found together with an overall pre-exponential factor k_i . (ii) The
 204 complete set of experimental data including both degreened and aged samples
 205 that differed in ZCuOH and Z₂Cu site densities was then used for evaluation
 206 of pre-exponential factors $k_{i,Z\text{CuOH}}$ and $k_{i,Z_2\text{Cu}}$, employing equation (10). In
 207 this second step, the previously obtained activation energy $E_{a,i}$ was already
 208 fixed. Furthermore, a binding condition was used that enforced the values of
 209 $k_{i,Z\text{CuOH}}$ and $k_{i,Z_2\text{Cu}}$ to provide the same overall pre-exponential factor k_i for
 210 the degreened catalyst as obtained in the first step.

211 In the following text, the results obtained with rate coefficient k_i decom-

212 posed to $k_{i,ZCuOH}$ and k_{i,Z_2Cu} according to equation (10), utilizing the actual
 213 site densities θ_{ZCuOH} and θ_{Z_2Cu} predicted by the hydrothermal aging kinetics
 214 r_{HTA} , Table 2, will be denoted as "predicted". These results were further com-
 215 pared to the "best fit" obtained with a single-parameter fitting of effective rate
 216 coefficient k_i^{eff} directly to the data measured for the aged samples. Thus, the k_i^{eff}
 217 represents the best possible fit for the given catalyst state independent of site
 218 concentrations, while equation (10) predicts the reaction rate from the actual
 219 ZCuOH and Z₂Cu site fractions.

220 4. Results

Figure 2: Fractions of ZCuOH and Z₂Cu sites during hydrothermal aging of the Cu/SSZ-13 catalyst sample at 600 °C (solid line) and 550 °C (dashed line) as predicted by the HTA model. Colored points mark the catalyst states examined in this work and black crosses experimental data from catalyst characterization

221 The simulated ZCuOH and Z₂Cu concentration evolution during mild hy-
 222 drothermal aging is shown in Figure 2. A simultaneous decrease in ZCuOH
 223 and an increase in Z₂Cu sites is predicted with hydrothermal aging time. The
 224 simulation results are in good agreement with the experimental data obtained
 225 by characterization techniques discussed in Section 2, see the black crosses in

Table 3: Concentrations of active sites at different stages of hydrothermal aging as predicted by the model

HTA time (h)	0	10	25
Coverages normalized by Ω_Z			
θ_{ZCuOH} (-)	0.355	0.272	0.194
θ_{Z_2Cu} (-)	0.215	0.380	0.536
θ_{ZH} (-)	0.430	0.348	0.270
Site concentrations per washcoat volume			
Cu as ZCuOH (mol/m ³)	297	228	163
Cu as Z ₂ Cu (mol/m ³)	90	159	224
Brønsted sites ZH (mol/m ³)	360	291	226

226 Figure 2. The corresponding values of site fractions in the degreened state and
 227 after 10 and 25 hours of aging are summarized in Table 3.

228 As already mentioned, the concentration of Cu sites in the form of Z₂Cu is
 229 $\frac{1}{2}\theta_{Z_2Cu}\Omega_Z$ because θ_{Z_2Cu} is based on the number of Z sites involved. The rate co-
 230 efficient for Cu migration during hydrothermal aging at 600 °C is $1.98 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$.
 231 Considering the activation energy $E_{a,HTA} = 175 \text{ kJ/mol}$ proposed by Daya et al.
 232 [27] for a similar type of Cu/SSZ-13 catalyst, our HTA rate corresponds to the
 233 pre-exponential factor $k_{HTA} = 5.85 \times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$. For comparison, Daya et al. [27]
 234 reported pre-exponential factor $k_{HTA} = 5.09 \times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$, which is close to the
 235 k_{HTA} value obtained from our characterization data.

236 Figure 2 also shows the evolution of ZCuOH and Z₂Cu site concentrations
 237 at 550 °C as predicted by the HTA model, considering the activation energy
 238 $E_{a,HTA} = 175 \text{ kJ/mol}$ [27]. Note that 550 °C was the maximum temperature
 239 reached only for the last 30 minutes during the reaction experiments. Thus, the
 240 catalyst aging during the reaction experiments was negligible compared to the
 241 HTA procedure lasting 10 or 25 hours at 600 °C.

242 After identification of the aging kinetics and quantification of ZCuOH and
 243 Z₂Cu sites, we focused on the kinetics of NH₃, NO, SO₂ and CO oxidation over

Figure 3: Steady-state conversions during NH_3 oxidation on the degreened and hydrothermally aged (HTA) Cu/SSZ-13 catalyst, wet conditions. Points – experimental data, dashed lines – simulation results with the rate coefficient k_i depending on θ_{ZCuOH} predicted by the HTA model, solid lines – the best fit with an effective rate coefficient k_i^{eff}

244 the degreened and hydrothermally aged samples. The kinetic parameters of
 245 individual reactions were evaluated using two approaches. The first approach
 246 used two independent pre-exponential factors for ZCuOH and Z_2Cu sites, equa-
 247 tion (10), enabling predictions of the aged catalyst activity based on the actual
 248 site concentrations. We started with the 1st-order dependence on site den-
 249 sity ($n = 1$) and then tested also the 2nd-order ($n = 2$) in equation (10) for
 250 comparison. The second approach aimed on the identification of an effective
 251 pre-exponential factor that provides the best fit of the experimental data at the
 252 given aging state, independent of the actual site concentrations.

253 Figure 3 shows the results of experiments and simulations for NH_3 oxidation
 254 on the degreened, 10 h, and 25 h aged samples. Almost no reaction is observed
 255 at 200 °C. With increasing temperature, the outlet NH_3 conversion gradually
 256 increases due to increasing reaction rate. The degreened catalyst exhibits the
 257 highest extent of NH_3 oxidation. Catalytic activity decreases for the 10 h and
 258 25 h aged samples, resulting in lower outlet NH_3 conversions. The simulated
 259 curves match the trends observed in experiments. For the 10 h aged sample,

Table 4: Evaluated kinetic parameters for the studied oxidation reactions considering 1st-order dependence on ZCuOH and Z₂Cu site concentrations, $n = 1$ in equation (10)

Reaction	Conditions	$k_{i,ZCuOH}$ (s ⁻¹)	k_{i,Z_2Cu} (s ⁻¹)	$k_i^{\text{degreened}}$ (mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	$E_{a,i}$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)
R1 (NH ₃)	wet	1.67×10^7	0	5.26×10^9	63.9
R2 (NO)	wet	1.56×10^4	0	4.64×10^6	41.4
R3 (SO ₂)	dry	1.71×10^3	0	5.08×10^5	29.1
R4 (CO)	wet	1.09×10^8	0	3.24×10^{10}	80.0
R4 (CO)	dry	1.42×10^7	0	4.22×10^9	64.9

260 the 1st-order prediction based on ZCuOH and Z₂Cu site concentrations (dashed
 261 curve in Figure 3) provides results close to the best possible fit of the experi-
 262 mental data (solid curve in Figure 3). For the 25 h aged sample, the deviation
 263 between the 1st-order predictive approach and the best fit of the measured data
 264 points increases – the actual activity is slightly lower than predicted. Never-
 265 theless, the prediction based on ZCuOH and Z₂Cu site concentrations is still
 266 reasonably good.

267 The evaluated kinetic parameters in Table 4 reveal that zero pre-exponential
 268 factor of NH₃ oxidation on Z₂Cu sites is identified by the optimization method
 269 for the 1st-order dependence in equation (10), suggesting that the catalyst ac-
 270 tivity is correlated just to the concentration of ZCuOH sites. Note, the value of
 271 zero for the parameter k_{i,Z_2Cu} is obtained when the optimization method only
 272 allows the parameter value to reach this physically meaningful limit. Formally,
 273 it would be possible to achieve results closer to the best fit in Figure 3 if there
 274 was a negative contribution of Z₂Cu sites in the 1st-order predictive model,
 275 but obviously this is not physically meaningful. Thus, the interpretation of the
 276 obtained results is: the decrease in catalytic activity observed in experiments
 277 corresponds to, and even slightly exceeds, the loss of ZCuOH sites in the tested
 278 sample. The remaining rows of Table 4 indicate that the same conclusion can
 279 also be made for the NO, SO₂, and CO oxidation reactions.

Considering the identified value of $k_{i,Z_2Cu} = 0$, equation (10) simplifies to:

$$k_i = k_{i,ZCuOH} \theta_{ZCuOH}^n \Omega_Z \quad (12)$$

so that the reaction rate coefficients effectively depend only on ZCuOH site concentration. As already explained, mild hydrothermal aging does not affect significantly the concentration of Z sites in the zeolite structure, hence Ω_Z is constant. The intrinsic rate coefficient on ZCuOH site $k_{i,ZCuOH}$ remains constant as well. When equation (12) for the aged catalyst is divided by the same equation using the parameters of the degreened catalyst, a simple equation is obtained that can be used for the k_i^{aged} prediction:

$$\frac{k_i^{\text{aged}}}{k_i^{\text{degreened}}} = \left(\frac{\theta_{ZCuOH}^{\text{aged}}}{\theta_{ZCuOH}^{\text{degreened}}} \right)^n \quad (13)$$

280

281 To test if the 2nd-order dependence on Cu site concentration reported at
282 lower temperatures [37] is relevant for the studied reactions in a broad temper-
283 ature range examined in this work, we repeated the simulations using $n = 2$ in
284 equation (13). The NH₃ conversion curves predicted by a 2nd-order model go
285 below the measured data, see the dotted lines in Figure 3. This indicates that
286 the loss of catalytic activity observed in the experiment is lower than would cor-
287 respond to the 2nd-order dependence on ZCuOH site concentration. However,
288 the 2nd-order predictions are a bit closer to the best fit compared to the 1st-
289 order predictions. The corresponding root mean square errors (RMSE) for the
290 simulated NH₃ conversions in Figure 3 are provided in Supplementary Material,
291 Table S1.

292 The measured and simulated outlet conversions during NO oxidation are
293 depicted in Figure 4. Note that the NO oxidation rate becomes limited by re-
294 action equilibrium above ca. 450 °C and the outlet NO conversion decreases at
295 temperatures above 500 °C, which is captured correctly by the model for both
296 the degreened and aged samples. The loss of NO oxidation activity predicted
297 for the aged sample using the 1st-order dependence on ZCuOH site concentra-
298 tion (dashed line) is very close to the best possible fit of the measured data

Figure 4: Steady-state conversions during NO oxidation on the degreened and hydrothermally aged (HTA) Cu/SSZ-13 catalyst, wet conditions. Points – experimental data, dashed lines – simulation results with the rate coefficient k_i depending on θ_{ZCuOH} predicted by the HTA model, solid lines – the best fit with an effective rate coefficient k_i^{eff}

299 (solid line). In contrast, the 2nd-order prediction results in conversions that are
 300 too low, overestimating the catalyst deactivation for NO oxidation. The corre-
 301 sponding root mean square errors (RMSE) for the simulated NO conversions in
 302 Figure 4 are provided in Supplementary Material, Table S2.

303 CO oxidation was examined both in dry (0% H₂O) and wet (7% H₂O) con-
 304 ditions, Figure 5. It can be seen that the presence of water affects the CO
 305 oxidation rate to a different extent on the degreened and aged samples. The de-
 306 greened sample exhibits somewhat lower activation energy under dry conditions
 307 (the corresponding E_a values are provided in Table 4), but the aged sample
 308 performs better under wet conditions, Figure 5a,b. Ambivalent effects of water
 309 depending on structural parameters of the zeolite cages were already reported
 310 for the low-temperature SCR reaction [47]. Water effects on the reaction kinetics
 311 may include both inhibition and promotion, which requires additional charac-
 312 terization of the catalyst structure and more detailed reaction mechanisms to
 313 be addressed in future studies. We can only speculate that water inhibits CO
 314 oxidation at lower-to-intermediate temperatures but acts as a CO oxidant at

Figure 5: Steady-state conversions during CO oxidation under a) dry and b) wet conditions on the degreened and hydrothermally aged (HTA) Cu/SSZ-13 catalyst. Points – experimental data, dashed lines – simulation results with the rate coefficient k_i depending on θ_{ZCuOH} predicted by the HTA model, solid lines – the best fit with an effective rate coefficient k_i^{eff}

Figure 6: Steady-state conversions during SO_2 oxidation on the degreened and hydrothermally aged (HTA) Cu/SSZ-13 catalyst, dry conditions. Points – experimental data, dashed lines – simulation results with the rate coefficient k_i depending on θ_{ZCuOH} predicted by the HTA model, solid lines – the best fit with an effective rate coefficient k_i^{eff}

315 high temperatures, which would explain the behavior observed in Figure 5a,b.
 316 For CO oxidation, the predictions using a 2nd-order dependence on ZCuOH site
 317 concentration match the experimental results much better than the 1st-order
 318 predictions. Under wet conditions, Figure 5b, the 2nd-order prediction is prac-
 319 tically identical with the best possible fit. For dry conditions, the measured
 320 outlet conversion is lower than predicted, which means that even the 2nd-order
 321 model underestimated the actual loss in catalytic activity. The corresponding
 322 root mean square errors (RMSE) for the simulated CO conversions in Figure 5
 323 are provided in Supplementary Material, Table S3.

324 SO_2 oxidation results under dry conditions are plotted in Figure 6. The
 325 corresponding experiment under wet conditions was not performed due to ex-
 326 tensive SO_x adsorption, formation of H_2SO_4 , extremely long times needed to
 327 reach steady state due to acid formation and inconsistency in closing the mass
 328 balance due to FTIR cell limitations. Similar to NO oxidation, SO_2 oxidation
 329 can be potentially limited by thermodynamic equilibrium at high conversions
 330 and increased temperatures. However, this limitation plays only a minor role

Table 5: Overall pre-exponential factors for the catalyst hydrothermally aged at 600 °C: k_i predicted by equation (13), using 1st-order ($n = 1$) or 2nd-order ($n = 2$) in ZCuOH site concentrations, compared to k_i^{eff} fitted directly to the measured data (best fit)

Reaction	Conditions	Aging (h)	predicted 1 st order	predicted 2 nd order	best fit
			k_i (mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	k_i (mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	k_i^{eff} (mol m ⁻³ s ⁻¹)
R1 (NH ₃)	wet	10	4.03×10^9	3.08×10^9	3.59×10^9
R1 (NH ₃)	wet	25	2.87×10^9	1.57×10^9	2.13×10^9
R2 (NO)	wet	25	2.53×10^6	1.38×10^6	2.23×10^6
R3 (SO ₂)	dry	25	2.78×10^5	1.52×10^5	2.71×10^5
R4 (CO)	wet	25	1.77×10^{10}	9.67×10^9	9.31×10^9
R4 (CO)	dry	25	2.31×10^9	1.26×10^9	6.42×10^8

331 under the studied range of operating conditions; just the last temperature point
332 is slightly affected. The decrease in SO₂ oxidation rate on the aged sample
333 predicted by the 1st-order model depending on the changes in ZCuOH sites
334 concentration matches the measured data and is practically identical to the
335 best possible fit, see the red dashed and solid line in Figure 6. The 2nd-order
336 predictions overestimate aging impact on SO₂ conversions, see the red dotted
337 line in Figure 6. The corresponding root mean square errors (RMSE) for the
338 simulated SO₂ conversions in Figure 6 are provided in Supplementary Material,
339 Table S4.

340 Table 5 and Figure 7 provide a summary comparison of predicted and fitted
341 rate coefficients k_i for NH₃, NO, SO₂, and CO oxidation for the hydrothermally
342 aged samples. Note that all k_i values in Figure 7 are normalized by the cor-
343 responding rate coefficient on the degreened sample, see $k_i^{\text{degreened}}$ in Table 4.
344 The "best fit" values closely reflect the measured reaction rates, while the pre-
345 dicted values relate the rate coefficients to the actual concentration of ZCuOH
346 sites, see equation (13) and Table 3. Direct comparison of the predicted rate
347 coefficients k_i to the best fitted k_i^{eff} reveals how appropriate the correlation be-
348 tween ZCuOH and the rate coefficient is. Additional measures in terms of root

Figure 7: Relative rate coefficients $k_i^{\text{aged}}/k_i^{\text{degreened}}$ as predicted by the hydrothermal aging model using 1st or 2nd order in ZCuOH (dark and light blue bars, respectively) and obtained by the best fit of the measured data (hatched bars). All the values are normalized by the corresponding rate coefficient on the degreened sample $k_i^{\text{degreened}}$ (red line as a reference)

349 mean square error are provided in Supplementary Material, Tables S1–S4. The
 350 predictive model assuming 1st-order dependence on ZCuOH site density is very
 351 close to the best fit for NO and SO₂ oxidation. The 1st-order prediction is less
 352 accurate in case of NH₃ oxidation, but still usable. Both 1st-order and 2nd-order
 353 provide comparable accuracy for NH₃ oxidation and the obtained results do not
 354 allow clear discrimination between them. The only case that is clearly better
 355 described by the 2nd-order dependence on ZCuOH site concentration is CO ox-
 356 idation, where the reaction rate observed experimentally on the aged catalyst
 357 is noticeably lower than the 1st-order prediction.

358 5. Conclusions

359 The developed kinetic model includes the gradual transformation of ZCuOH
 360 sites into Z₂Cu during mild hydrothermal aging of a Cu/SSZ-13 catalyst and
 361 its impact on NH₃, NO, SO₂, and CO oxidation rates in a broad range of tem-
 362 peratures. The combined experimental and modeling results suggest negligible
 363 rates of the studied reactions on Z₂Cu sites and a close correlation of the overall

364 reaction rates to the concentration of ZCuOH sites, which is of 1st order for NO,
365 NH₃ and SO₂ oxidation, while CO oxidation exhibits a 2nd-order dependence.
366 The model provides a reasonably accurate prediction of the aged catalyst's ac-
367 tivities for NH₃, NO, SO₂, and CO oxidation reactions as the reactions follow
368 similar trends with mild hydrothermal aging. The proposed coupling of Cu site
369 transformation kinetics with the kinetics of oxidation reactions provides a pow-
370 erful tool for predictive simulations of SCR catalyst performance in terms of
371 changes with time and under realistic operating conditions. In particular, the
372 changes in NH₃ oxidation rates are crucial for precise urea dosing and SO₂ oxi-
373 dation represents a key step in the sulfur poisoning mechanism, and all reactions
374 are important to consider for close-coupled SCR configurations.

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378 **Nomenclature**

	a	momentum flux correction factor, 1
	c_p	heat capacity, $\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$
	c	molar concentration, mol m^{-3}
	D	diameter, m
	E_a	activation energy, J mol^{-1}
	ΔH_r	reaction enthalpy, J mol^{-1}
	k_i	pre-exponential factor of rate coefficient for reaction i , s^{-1}
	k_{HTA}	pre-exponential factor of hydrothermal aging rate, s^{-1}
	k_c	mass transfer coefficient, m s^{-1}
	k_h	heat transfer coefficient, $\text{J s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2} \text{K}^{-1}$
379	L	length, m
	n	order in Cu sites, 1
	N	total number of elements in a set, 1
	R	universal gas constant, $\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$
	r_i	reaction rate per volume of catalytic washcoat, $\text{mol s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-3}$
	S	sum of squares, 1
	T	temperature, K
	t	time variable
	u	linear velocity, m s^{-1}
	y	molar fraction, 1
	z	spatial coordinate
380	<i>Greek letters</i>	
	ε	porosity, 1
	λ	heat conductivity, $\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$
	ν	stoichiometric coefficient, 1
381	φ_w	volume fraction of catalytic washcoat in solid phase, 1
	ρ	density, kg m^{-3}
	θ	surface site coverage, 1
	Ω_Z	aluminum site concentration in zeolite framework, mol m^{-3} washcoat

382 *Subscripts and superscripts*

eff	effective
exp	measured (experimental)
g	gas
<i>i</i>	index of reaction
in	inlet
<i>j</i>	index of measured data point
383 <i>k</i>	index of gas component
<i>m</i>	index of surface component
out	outlet
s	solid
w	catalytic washcoat
Z	aluminum site in zeolite framework

384 *Abbreviations*

ASC	ammonia slip catalyst
cc-SCR	close coupled selective catalytic reduction of NO _x
cpsi	channels per square inch
DOC	diesel oxidation catalyst
DPF	diesel particulate filter
DRIFTS	diffuse reflectance infrared Fourier-transform spectroscopy
FTIR	Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy
385 GHSV	gas hourly space velocity
HTA	hydrothermal aging
RMSE	root mean square error
SCR	selective catalytic reduction of NO _x
SEM	scanning electron microscopy
TPD	temperature programmed desorption
TPR	temperature programmed reduction

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